

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE ACTIVITIES TO DEVELOP STUDENTS’ COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Akhmadalieva Khosiyatposhsho Abdukhayotovna
Head and Acting Associate Professor of the Department
“Theoretical Aspects of the English Language”
strong-girl5@mail.ru

Abstract. The article reveals the use of communicative activities as one of the most effective ways to improve students’ communicative competence. And also indicates ways to create a real English environment through the implementation of language in practice, ways for students to communicate freely without fear of making mistakes and express their opinions on the spot.

Key words: *English lessons, communicative competence, modern communicative activities, student-centered approach, English environment, free communication.*

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается использование коммуникативных активностей как одного из наиболее эффективных способов улучшения коммуникативной компетенции студентов. Также указываются способы создания настоящей английской среды через практическое использование языка, способы для свободного общения студентов без страха допустить ошибки и высказывать свои мнения на месте.

Ключевые слова: *Уроки английского языка, коммуникативная компетенция, современные коммуникативные активности, студенческий центрированный подход, английская среда, свободное общение.*

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini takomillashtirishning samarali usullaridan biri kommunikativ mashqlar yoritilgan. Shuningdek, amalda tilni qo‘llash orqali haqiqiy ingliz tili muhitini yaratish, o‘quvchilarning xato qilishdan qo‘rqmay erkin muloqotga kirishish yo‘llari va o‘z fikrlarini o‘z o‘rnida ifoda etish usullari ko‘rib chiqilgan.

Tayanch so‘z va tushunchalar: *Ingliz tili darslari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, zamonaviy kommunikativ mashqlar, talaba- markazli yondashuv, ingliz tili muhiti, erkin muloqot.*

The main goal of teaching English is defined as the formation and development of students’ communicative competence and teaching them to practice the language. It is apparent that the task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow them to demonstrate their activity and creativity, and to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Formation of linguistic competence among students in English classes can be done with the help of exercises. Mastering the skill of forming word combinations means mastering the ability to independently

understand the meaning of an unfamiliar person based on the knowledge of the meanings of their components and the corresponding word formation pattern. Everyone who learns a foreign language should first master the vocabulary necessary for communication in this language, focusing on preparing their speech for communicative activities and achieving clarity and consistency in speech. If students learn to understand the meaning of phrases and sentences, they will have the skills to express their thoughts in writing and orally, they can substitute one word for another without hesitation in their speech, use synonyms [1; p. 38].

Learning a language is usually done through practice. The main content of the exercises is focused on the formation, formation and development of skills in speech activities of language and speech learners. Exercises are an educational tool that captures, facilitates and accelerates the types of speech activity [2; p.132]. During exercise, its dynamic and static aspects are studied.

The activity material in statics can be a letter, sound, word, graphic, sentence or text and is a teaching-methodical category marked with a specific number or letter, which is a direct component of the lesson. Dynamics activity is understood as the activity of a foreign language teacher in the classroom, from writing or pronouncing letters to perceiving and understanding the text, expressing one's thoughts freely [3; p.82].

The role of the exercise system in learning foreign languages, especially English, is invaluable. I.V. Rakhmanov uses all sets of exercises as a system of two types: language and speech exercises, V.A. Bukhbinder divides into informational, operational and motivational types. E. I. Passov [4; p. 40] at one time put forward the opinion that any exercises have a communicative, linguistic and psychological nature. In his opinion, communicative exercises are divided into real communicative and conditional communicative exercises. If real communicative exercises appear in the process of communication, conditional communicative exercises require the creation of a communication situation during training. In the researches of E.I. Passov [5; p.14-16], we can observe a system consisting of three directions in accordance with the communicative aspect directed at learning a foreign language:

1. *A set of exercises aimed at building communication skills.*
2. *A collection of exercises aimed at improving communication skills.*
3. *A set of exercises to develop personal communication skills using the learned lexical material.*

I.V. Rakhmanov [6; p. 187] and the exercise system includes language and speech exercises, receptive and reproductive, aspectual and complex exercises, educational and purely communicative exercises, preparation and control exercises; according to the nature of exercises: oral and written, monolingual and bilingual, mechanical and creative, class and home exercises, individual, pair, choir exercises; based on the selected material, he proposed to classify it as: dialogic and monologic speech exercises. N. Shukin [7; p. 416] divided the exercise system into 3 types as follows: according to the offer (*control, complex, receptive*); according to their descriptive character (*dialogic and monologic*),

according to the method of execution (*oral/written, in the classroom/at home, individually/together*). Voluntary ability, skill formation develops during activity and training. The exercise, according to the purpose, includes activities aimed at students in the process of language acquisition and based on language material in accordance with speech activity. This process is the basis for the formation of language skills and abilities. Uzbek methodist J. Jalolov mentioned[1; p. 58] exercises types of speech activity (*speaking, reading, writing and listening comprehension*) and language material (*vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation*) are also called exercises. It is also divided into oral and written exercises. Oral type dialogue, monologue, lexical, grammatical and pronunciation assignments; and the written form is used to write an opinion. In the research work of Y.A. Lagay and exercises are divided into 3 types: *receptive exercises* (preparatory, analytical and imitative), *reproductive exercises* (synthetic, semi-constructive), *productive exercises* (constructive and transformational).

Therefore, actions that serve to improve and strengthen the educational process of practical importance, which are carried out sequentially or separately, are called exercises in the educational process. The exercises are focused on solid mastery of the subject during the lesson and are selected by the teacher in accordance with the knowledge levels of the students. Exercises and tasks aimed at improving all types of communicative competence are the subject of research. We recommended types of receptive, reproductive and productive communicative exercises aimed at improving communicative competence [8; p.464].

“**Guided interview**” is one of the effective communicative activities implemented in English lessons carried out in two stages. In the first stage, they are organized in small groups and given different topics. Answers will be written on the topic, and students will create logical questions together. In particular, the following questions will be written on the topic “Job interview”:

- Tell me about yourself.
- What experience do you have in this field?
- What do co-workers say about you?
- What are your preferences?
- What have done to improve your knowledge this year?
- What foreign languages do you know?
- How long would you expect to work with us if you hired?
- Tell us why would we hire you?

In the second stage, students pair up and formally present a 2-3 minutes real interview based on the topic given in practice. At the end, students analyze the achievements and shortcomings (Feedback) and summarize the topic.

“**Optimists and pessimists**” is modern communicative activity that the group is divided into optimists and pessimists, and a topic is chosen for discussion. For example, on the topic "equation", optimists talk about the definition of equations and properties of

equations, while pessimists talk about one and two unknown types of equations. During the discussion, the pessimists give the answers of the optimists, and the optimists, as an addition to them, write written answers in groups, and at the end of the game, the opinions are summarized (see figure 1)

“*From A to Z*” is also one of the successful communicative activities which students discuss the topic in small groups and write a summary. Then the dialogue is played for them to listen to and they compose the dialogue in alphabetical order. Then they read it in roles, and at the end, the students point out the shortcomings and mistakes, the students evaluate each other's work (Peer Correction), and the topic is summarized (see figure 2):

Actually, what can you say about using mobile phones in classes. To my mind, it interrupts you.

Do you think so? We use phones only for our study. Because we often face unfamiliar words, so we use google translation.

But sometimes, we spend a lot of time for social networks in front of it

Certainly. It is a pity that you are wasting your precious time for unnecessary things instead of studying.

“*Art Gallery*” is one of the innovative activities that is implemented in English classes successfully. In this communicative exercise, the teacher brings a lot of information on a free topic in a paper version, for example: on the topic of “*Seven Wonders of the World*” about each wonder from 1 sheet in total Brings 7 sheets of information and sticks them on different places of the walls of the room. Then, before starting the exercise, teacher mentions the students to go back to their seats and briefly write down the main information in their notebooks in English after reading each one, because there is a lot of information there. It is strictly forbidden to carry a notebook or paper next to the pasted information. Students go around the room and sit down after reading all the information. Then, based on the given information, the teacher presents the prepared questions and the students’ debates begin. After one question is fully answered, the discussion of the next question begins. As a result, students communicate with the information they have learned and strengthen it.

In the “*Free writing*” activity, students briefly write their thoughts on a given life situation (Uzbek Vignette) in a notebook within 2 minutes. After the time is up, the students’ answers will be heard and then the discussion will begin. All students express their attitude to the presented situation and exchange opinions. All ideas are taken into

account, and finally, the ideas are summarized and concluded in a situation-specific manner (see figure 3):

Read the following Uzbek Vignettes and show your attitude to them based on life experiences

A few days ago, to your group was added a new pupil Bobur and he couldn't get on well with another student Bekzod. They always argue and even had a fight three days before. As a group member, how can you solve this problem and make them friends?

Recently, Sanjar and his family have moved to the New York from Fergana because of his father's job. He joined to new class and he has a lot of problems while communicating with his friends and daily life, because he has pronunciation problems and it is hard to explain some things to people around him. As you notice he is in tough situation. What must he do? Please help him.

Based on given communicative activities, we tried to classify the types of activities used to develop students' communicative competence from the types of speech activity, from the system of activities performed in language dynamics and forming skills and competencies in speech activity [9; p.85]. Above mentioned activities are receptive, reproductive and productive types of exercises. Taking these classifications as a basis, the use of receptive, reproductive, productive exercises aimed at the formation of skills and competencies in speech activity for students of the first year of integration of speech activities, and for the second year, based on the dynamics of language skills on topics we recommend using a system of situational-communicative, creative and integrative exercises aimed at developing communicative competence.

In conclusion, communicative competence plays a leading role in the formation of students' communicative skills as an urgent issue in the rules of teaching foreign languages. In the practice of teaching foreign languages, a set of exercises and tasks focused on communicative activity is widely used. Mastering speech skills is a process of practicing speech events, starting from words, phrases, and large-scale complex texts. In the process of formation of communication skills, the skills of mastering lexical materials, developing skills through exercises are formed and are sequentially placed in the rules of professional orientation. The level of formation of oral speech is based on a psychological systematic sequence in the process of memorization, comprehension and pronunciation based on lexical skills, and semantics, reinforcement and repetition processes are characteristic for all stages. All elements of the language layer are interconnected. Development of all components of communicative competence in lessons, focusing more on the development of student-to-student communication, constantly creating opportunities to work on the shortcomings of students and eliminate them, negotiating on topics related to all areas of life improvement of students' communicative competence is achieved by starting to work in groups to involve all students at the same time. As a result, in the process of communication, students convey their thoughts to the interlocutor freely,

without difficulties, without speech interruptions, without stopping, in a clear, clear and understandable way.

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